

ACUTE - Accessibility and Connectivity Knowledge Hub for Urban Transformation in Europe

WP1 – ENUAC Cross Research Community

D1.4.2 Compilation and analysis of European projects on urban transport with a focus on accessibility and connectivity.

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Authors: Enya Reichmuth
Alain L’Hostis

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Project Partners

Organisation	Country
University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna BOKU	AUSTRIA
Université Gustav Eiffel UEiffel	FRANCE
Centre d’études et d’expertise sur les risques, l’environnement, la mobilité et l’aménagement Cerema	FRANCE
Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies LBTU	LATIVA
University of Latvia LU	LATIVA
Research Institutes of Sweden RISE	SWEDEN
University of Westminster UoW	UNITED KINGDOM
Malmö University MAU	SWEDEN
Grazer Energieagentur GmbH, Graz Energy Agency GEA	AUSTRIA
VTI/Sweden’s national centre for research and education on public transport K2	SWEDEN
Power Circle PC	SWEDEN
University of Innsbruck UIBK	AUSTRIA

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Glossary

Abbreviation

15mC	15-minute City
DUT	Driving Urban Transitions
EIT	European Institute for Innovation and Technology
ENUAC	ERA-NET Urban Accessibility and Connectivity
EU	European Union
FP	EU framework programme for research and innovation
JPI	Joint Programming Initiative
KA	Key Area of Action
R&I	Research and innovation
SUMP	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan

Executive Summary

This report is an analysis of a compilation of 203 transnational research and innovation projects centring around accessible and sustainable urban transport. Projects were thematically selected based on the objectives of the 15 *ERA-NET Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC) projects* funded by **JPI Urban Europe** and **Horizon 2020**. These objectives involve accessibility and inclusivity, sustainable urban mobility and logistics, innovative technologies, and activation of urban spaces and infrastructure.

Both the project compilation and the analysis were produced in the context of the *Accessibility and Connectivity knowledge hub for Urban Transformation in Europe (ACUTE)*.

The project compilations contains projects from various European funding programmes, the projects' time horizon spans from 2002 to 2024 as start date. The information provided for each project include full title, relevant websites as sources and for further information, project coordinator and contact information, number of project partners, duration, a categorisation to "Key Areas of Action", keywords, case studies and a short description. Project partners were recorded in a spreadsheet.

One focus of the analysis were the project consortia and partner-based connections between projects. These connections, that emerge when an organisation participates in two or more of the examined projects. were visualised in a network graph. The majority of the over 2000 organisations recorded for their project participation were only involved in one project. 16 organisations participated in ten or more projects and thereby significantly impact the number of project connections through shared partners. Differences regarding consortium size and connections were observed between the funding programmes.

The analysis of the projects in their relation to the Key Areas of Action, a concept by the **DUT partnership** for their 15-minute City Pathway, revealed three topics that received little attention among the 203 projects: sustainable solutions for longer trips between cities or for leisure, support for neighbourhood economies and the use of airspace and underground for logistics. Frequently addressed topics of the Key Areas were related to urban governance and experiments, access to sustainable mobility, new technologies and participation of civil society and stakeholders.

The third aspect of the analysis was the availability of project information and resources. This was observed as an issue for a number of projects, with project websites often disappearing some time after the project ended. Some programme websites and repositories succeed in providing a high level of information and resources, while others are not intended to offer access to documents and other resources. Missing and conflicting information also posed challenges for the data collection. Different kind of structural and project- or website-specific problems are explained in a separate chapter.

The report concludes with recommendations for for funding programmes and ongoing projects as well as future directions describing possible applications of the project compilation and the findings of zhis analysis.

1. Introduction

All over Europe, transport is not sufficiently sustainable, accessible, safe, or smart. A radical change with sustainable and innovative solutions is needed to overcome these challenges. This is why under the funding programme **Horizon 2020** around €6 billion were allocated to the Societal Challenge “Smart, Green and Integrated Transport” (European Commission, 2014). This enabled funding for many projects.

The *ERA-NET Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC)* is also supported by **Horizon 2020** under the ERA-NET Cofund scheme. The first call, launched by the **Joint Programming Initiative Urban Europe (JPI Urban Europe)** in 2019, funded fifteen research and innovation (R&I) projects. The call and the projects pursue the goal to enhance urban accessibility, connectivity and sustainable and inclusive mobility. Sustainable urban accessibility and connectivity in this context refer to how easily activities can be reached within an urban transport system while minimising environmental harm. Network connectivity represents the directness of routes and the integration of different modes of transport. Both passenger and freight transport are considered (JPI Urban Europe, 2021).

But many projects dealt with sustainable and inclusive urban transport before, and more will be funded in the future. It is crucial for future R&I efforts to focus on research gaps and build upon existing knowledge and experiences to tackle unsolved challenges. This would enable a more efficient use of funding budgets, directing resources towards areas with the greatest need and potential impact. It would accelerate problem-solving and innovation by avoiding duplication of efforts.

Overcoming the fragmentation of results is also an aim of *ACUTE*, the *Accessibility and Connectivity knowledge hub for Urban Transformation in Europe*, which was created to assist the ENUAC programme and projects and strategically support the **Driving Urban Transitions Partnership (DUT Partnership)** (JPI Urban Europe, n.d.-b).

In this context, a compilation of projects from different funding programmes was created. It is thematically based on the *ENUAC projects*, which involves accessibility and inclusivity, sustainable urban mobility and logistics, innovative technologies, and activation of urban spaces and infrastructure. The collection contains relevant information of each project, including participating organisations and online sources for more details. This document is meant to explain the methodology behind the project compilation and aims to analyse it. It looks at the project consortia and their structure, analyses topics and approaches based on a conceptual framework by the **DUT Partnership** and discusses the availability of information and research outputs of the projects. One chapter describes different kind of problems which were observed during the data collection. Finally, recommendations based on the relevant findings as well as possible applications for the project compilation are given.

2. Methodology

This study is based on a compilation of 203 R&I projects, which is the annex of this deliverable. First the methodological approach for the project compilation is described, beginning with the identification and selection of projects, followed by the data collection. Then the approaches for this analysis of the project compilation are explained.

2.1. Project selection

The *ENUAC projects* provided the thematic orientation with accessibility, connectivity and sustainable transport in an urban context. Relevant topics tackled in the projects cover inclusion, justice, innovative technologies like geofencing or autonomous vehicles, shared mobility, change of mobility behaviour, use of public space, sustainable logistics, and electric mobility.

As **JPI Urban Europe**'s calls usually require consortia involving participants from three or more countries, which should also represent different types of participants (JPI Urban Europe, n.d.-a), this criteria regarding consortia has been adopted for the selection of the projects.

Starting from the ENUAC projects, the compilation contains projects from **JPI Urban Europe** and its successor, the **DUT Partnership**. The two other main sources for the identification of relevant projects were **CIVITAS** and **POLIS**. In a survey by *ACUTE* conducted among participants of the *ENUAC* projects, these two were mentioned frequently as networks related to their research field. With the **CIVITAS initiative**, projects funded by the **EU framework programmes for research and innovation (FPs)** were incorporated. **POLIS** is a network of cities and regions dedicated to sustainable urban mobility. Through **POLIS** as project partner also projects from Interreg and **EIT Urban Mobility**, a few projects not related to any of these funding programmes were added. For a better representation of **Interreg** and **EIT Urban Mobility**, some more of their projects additionally were selected.

Thereby the project compilation represents a broad landscape of research projects in the area of urban transport and development, including some projects with a focus on technology rather than accessibility. The 203 projects consist of:

- 56 projects funded by **JPI Urban Europe** – including the 15 *ENUAC projects* and *ACUTE*,
- 71 **CIVITAS** projects funded by the **FPs** – considering all 70 projects which started until June 2024 and the current support project *MUSE*,
- 22 more projects funded by the **FPs** – identified through **POLIS**,
- 12 projects funded by different **Interreg** programmes,
- 14 projects funded by **EIT Urban Mobility**,
- 23 projects funded by the **DUT Partnership** – representing all projects in the 15-minute City (15mC) Pathway in the *DUT Call 2022*, and
- 5 projects not related to these funding programmes.

The project collection is structured into the different funding programmes: **JPI Urban Europe, FPs** (including **CIVITAS**), **Interreg, EIT Urban Mobility, DUT Partnership** and a short section for the five remaining projects. The funding programmes were further divided into calls, periods or programmes, because a standardised classification was not practicable. Within their section, projects were sorted chronologically according to their start date. A brief description of the funding programmes is included in their respective sections of the project compilation.

2.2. Data collection

The project compilation was created through collecting and synthesising information on the selected projects from various publicly available online sources. This involves the project website if available, the website of programmes and some repositories. Sometimes websites of partners or documents provided missing data. The information collected about each project was compiled into a structured table with the following data points:

- Project acronym and full title
- Project website and other relevant online sources
- Call under which the project was funded (in some cases programmes or alternative details)
- Project coordinator and contact information
- Project partners
- Duration (in months)
- Start and end dates
- Key Areas
- Keywords (significant words and phrases to describe the project according to the indicated websites)
- Case studies
- A project description

Project partners were recorded in a spreadsheet. The final 203 projects involved 2026 partners. Different languages and possible changes to the names of the organisations were considered in the allocation to avoid duplicate entries. Special attention was given to identify the specific departments or research groups from participating universities, through additional research on university and project websites. In some cases, however, it was not possible to precisely determine the involved divisions. As a result of this approach, the number of partners stated in the sources often does not correspond to the number determined in the spreadsheet, when multiple divisions from the same university participated in one project. Discrepancies can also occur due to differing information in the sources used.

Another information provided for each project is a classification to the Key Areas of Action (KAs) which is a concept developed by the **DUT Partnership** as a thematic guide for their 15mC Transition Pathway. Each of the four KAs comprises several subcategories as shown in Figure 1 (DUT Partnership, 2024b).

Figure 1: Key Areas of the 15-minute City Transition Pathway by the DUT Partnership. Source: (DUT Partnership, 2024) (p. 7).

The KAs including subcategories relevant to a project were inserted in the project tables and also recorded in a spreadsheet. Also, sometimes only the primary KA was selected, when the project obviously matched with the KA, but in a different aspect than the subcategories or not enough information was available to go further into detail.

To highlight specific topics or project structures, a short “Focus” was added to the KAs. This was mainly relevant for projects with a more technological focus or support actions.

2.3. Analysis

The collected projects were analysed in regards to three aspects: the project consortia, the KAs and the availability of information and resources. Another chapter outlines various problems faced during the data collection. In all sections, selected or exemplary projects are mentioned. Relevant project websites or

subpages are referred to via footnotes. Also considered are occurring differences between funding programmes as well as possible limitations of the project compilation and analysis.

The analysis of project consortia is based on the spreadsheet created which lists participating organisations and allocates them to projects. From this, the number of projects in which an organisation participates and the size of project consortia can be determined. In this context, a network graph was produced for the visualisation of partner-based connections between projects. Partner names are preferably mentioned in English in this analysis, instead of the longer label in the spreadsheet. An additional chapter describes findings of a survey conducted by *ACUTE* regarding the *ENUAC projects* and their relation to other projects and expert networks.

In terms of the KAs, trends and research gaps among the 203 projects are discussed. For all subcategories, different topics and examples for projects and approaches are described.

The next section addresses project websites and compares project information provided by funding programmes and repositories. A project website refers in this sense to a website dedicated to a single project which provides detailed explanations and can be seen as its official web presence apart from its subpages on the funding programme website and repositories. The continued existence of the project websites was checked in September 2024. For completed projects the availability of deliverables, tools and other resources was of special importance. The documents found were gathered and from this, projects with a low amount of discovered resources and outcomes were identified.

The last chapter of the results describes problems noted that impact effective accessing of information and resources and caused complications for the data collection.

Based on these problems and other findings of the analysis, recommendations for funding programmes, projects as well as for future research and possible applications of the project compilation are provided in the end.

3. Results

3.1. Project consortia

Project consortia were recorded in a spreadsheet. Based on this data, conclusions can be drawn regarding the participation of organisations, thereby identifying the most active organisations, and connections between project consortia through shared partners.

Project partner organisations

2026 partners were identified, which show different degrees of participation in the projects: 76 % of them participated in only one of the projects examined, while some organisations are part of many project consortia.

The organisation which participates in the most projects is **POLIS** (62 projects). This is not surprising, as **POLIS** was initially used to identify relevant projects. **Rupprecht Consult-Forschung & Beratung GmbH** follows with 25 projects, 20 of them in cooperation with **POLIS**. Other organisations which were involved in ten or more projects are:

- **BKK Centre for Budapest Transport** (15 projects)
- **Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) – Hellenic Institute of Transport (HIT)** (14 projects)
- **Eurocities ASBL** (13 projects)
- **City of Amsterdam** (12 projects)
- **European Road Transport Telematics Implementation Coordination Organisation – Intelligent Transport Systems & Services Europe (ERTICO – ITS Europe)** (12 projects)
- **Aimsun SLU** (11 projects)

- **Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) – Electromobility research centre (MOBI)** (11 projects)
- **AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH** (10 projects)
- **City of Gothenburg** (10 projects)
- **City of Stockholm** (10 projects)
- **ICLEI European Secretariat GmbH** (10 projects)
- **Institute of Transport Economics (TOI)** (10 projects)
- **International Association of Public Transport (UITP)** (10 projects)
- **Roma Servizi per la Mobilità s.r.l.** (10 projects).

Project consortium size

While these most frequently involved partners play crucial roles in connecting multiple projects, as will be demonstrated in the following sections, the overall size of each consortium also impacts project connectivity. The project consortia with the most partners can be found in the projects

- *eBRT2030* (55 partners)
- *DISCO* (47 partners)
- *metaCCAZE* (44 partners)
- *GEMINI* (43 partners)
- *UPPER* (41 partners)
- *deployEMDS* (41 partners)
- *URBANE* (40 partners)
- *SPINE* (40 partners).

These eight projects, all initiated in 2022 or later, are part of the **Horizon Europe** programme, with the exception of *deployEMDS*. The projects with the largest consortia of the other funding programmes are *SmartHubs* for **JPI Urban Europe** (34 partners), *eHUBS* for **Interreg** (20 partners), *LivingLAPT* for **EIT Urban Mobility** (17 partners) and *DREAMS* for the **DUT Partnership** (28 partners). With three partners, the consortia of *CASUAL*, *COCOMO* and *DVECE* are the smallest. Their funding programmes **EIT Urban Mobility** and **JPI Urban Europe** have the highest share of project consortia with less than 10 partners.

Consortia connections

The variations in consortium sizes are also clearly visible in Figure 2, with the node size proportional to the number of partners. The graph illustrates a network of project connections through shared partners. Such consortia connections emerge when an organisation participates, either over time or simultaneously, in two or more projects. The nodes of the graph represent the projects, with the size proportional to consortium size and the colour indicating the associated funding programme. The darker and the wider the line connecting the nodes, the more partners two projects share with each other.

Not surprisingly, large project consortia are likely to have a high number of partners participating in other projects. However, more important than the consortium size for connections to many projects is the participation of **POLIS** and the other most frequently involved partners named above. Eight of them are united in the project *UPPER*, which is connected to 104 other projects and located in the centre of the graph.

Figure 2: Network graph of the projects connected through shared project partners.

POLIS may be responsible for many consortia connections, but not for their strength, meaning how many shared partners connect two projects. The most connections between projects are weak, arising from a single shared partner. With 11 partners in common, *DISCO* and *URBANE* have the strongest connection, followed by:

- *SmarterHubs* and *DREAMS* (9 partners),
- *ELIPTIC* and *eBRT2030* (8 partners),
- *CIVIC* and *MIMIC* (7 partners),
- *SmarterLabs* and *SPECIFIC EASTER* (7 partners),
- *FLOW* and *UPPER* (7 partners) and
- *ECCENTRIC* and *SCALE-UP* (7 partners).

These are on the one hand projects with large consortia, making overlaps more likely. On the other hand, it shows successful collaborations which were taken further in new projects. This was likely the case in the two projects on sustainable construction logistics *CIVIC* and *MIMIC*, and the **JPI Urban Europe** projects *SmartHubs* and *SmarterLabs* with the new projects of the **DUT Partnership** *DREAMS* and *SPECIFIC*.

More interesting than the total numbers of connections to other projects, are the figures relative to project size. For example, there are some projects (*SmarterLabs*, *MIMIC*, *U-PASS*, *COCOMO*, *2MOVE2*, *FastTrack*, *UrbFRail*, *SUMI*), whose partners all are involved in more projects. The most connections relative to their consortium size are held by *APOLLO-EU*, *NICHES+*, *SUMI*, *WeCount*, *REFORM* and *FRESH*, projects with small consortia that include **POLIS**.

Nevertheless, there are a few projects with poor connections. *GUST* and *MAAT* don't share any partner with other projects, the projects *LISTEN* and *Play!UC* are only connected to each other. These four projects can be found separated from the others on the top right of the graph. Still, but loosely attached to the large project cluster are the projects *me²*, *SIMETRI*, *JUSTICE* and *MULTIGINATION*, which can be found rather at the edges, expect for *SIMETRI*, which is near its connected project *HARMONY*. Projects sharing partners with two other projects are *CONCOORD*, *SortedMobility*, *SUCCESS (FP6)* and *Inclusify*. These low-connected projects mainly belong to **JPI Urban Europe** and the **DUT Partnership**. Looking at the graph, its lower and right parts, where most projects of these two funding programmes are located, are less dense and show weaker connections. This comes especially evident in the graph when neglecting connections through only one shared partner, as in Figure 3, where only few connections remain in the lower graph and its outer areas. One reason for **JPI Urban Europe** and **DUT Partnership** projects being quite separated from the other projects is the near absence of the eight most frequently involved partners in their consortia. Also, the project *UrbFRail* can be found in the lower part of the graph, outstanding as the only included Interreg project without participation of **POLIS**.

Limitations

This shows quite well the bias from using **POLIS** as source for finding projects. However, this organisation only participates in two of the 14 **EIT Urban Mobility** projects included and still most of them have multiple overlaps with other consortia, located quite in the centre of the graph. Even the thematically relatively distinct *ISA-FIT* would be well connected to other projects without **POLIS**.

One limitation of these findings is their dependency on the considered divisions of the organisations, as they affect the way project participation and consortium size is counted. For instance, in the case of the **Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)** the participating department could only be identified for one project, causing a count of six projects for the general **BME** entry. If more university divisions were identified, the projects of the university and the resulting connections between the projects would be split, as for example the **Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)**. **VUB** is represented by seven divisions units, each with participation in two or more projects. If their participation would be united to a single count, **VUB** would be a partner in 18 projects. Also, for other types of organisations several divisions were stated as project partners, as city administrations for the **City of Stockholm**.

It is also important to note, that for a project to be active in a city in form of a case study of living lab, official participation of the city itself is not necessary. The city can also be represented by related entities like public transport authorities.

Figure 3: Network graph of the projects connected through at least two shared project partners.

3.2. ENUAC project mapping survey: The role of experts networks

During the ACUTE project a survey dedicated at understanding the uses and needs of the 15 ENUAC projects was conducted. Question 14 of this survey was “Name up to five projects (international, national, regional) you know which are related to your project at the European, national or city level”. Additional sources for the following network graphs were the proposals and first year progress reports of the projects.

The analysis of the relationships between projects, as illustrated in Figure 4, shows the importance of a series of experts networks, notably: **CROW**, **ALICE**, **CIVITAS**, **POLIS**, **ELTIS** and **K2**.

Sources:

- Survey Q14« Name up to five projects (international, national, regional) you know which are related to your project at the European, national or city level »
- Proposals
- Progress reports

Made with Tulip Software

Figure 4: Relationships of the 15 ENUAC projects between each other, policies and networks.

15 ENUAC projects ■

Referring to :

- Each other
- Policies ●
- Networks ★

Figure 5 gives a complete view of the network and reveals the complexity of the interrelations between projects, as well as the connection to existing knowledge at local, national and international scales.

Sources:

- Survey Q14« Name up to five projects (international, national, regional) you know which are related to your project at the European, national or city level »
- Proposals
- Progress reports

Made with Tulip Software

Figure 5: Relationships of the 15 ENUAC projects between each other, projects (European, national, local), policies and networks.

15 ENUAC projects ■

Referring to :

- Each other
- European projects ◆
- National projects ◆
- Local projects ◆
- Policies ●
- Networks ★

Comparison of ENUAC project mapping survey and compilation results

Connections between ENUAC projects

According to the analysis of the relationships between projects based on the survey, proposals and progress reports, *SortedMobility*, *ASAP* and *DyMoN* don't refer to other *ENUAC projects*. The partner-based analysis however shows connections of *ASAP* with *GeoSense* and *SortedMobility* with *EASIER*. Four projects don't possess any connections through shared partners.

Networks

From the networks referred to in the survey, proposals and progress reports, **CIVITAS** and **POLIS** were used for the identification of projects for the project compilation. The networks **ALICE**, **CROW** and **K2** appeared as project partners. However, among the *ENUAC projects*, only **CROW** is an official project partner of *SmartHubs*.

European projects

More than a third of the European projects the *ENUAC projects* referred to are part of the project compilation. Especially *SmartHubs*, *ASAP* and *EX-TRA* indicated many projects that can be found in the project compilation.

3.3. Key areas of action

After examining the structure of project consortia and partners, this chapter shifts attention to the content and thematic scope of the projects themselves. The projects are categorised by the Key Areas, which are described in detail in the 15mC Position Paper by the **DUT Partnership** (2024). By mapping project activities to the KAs, focal points and research gaps among the 203 projects can be highlighted. The following section provides a detailed analysis of each KA and its corresponding subcategories. Selected projects serve as examples to illustrate the diverse approaches within each KA. Table 1 summarises the number of projects associated with subcategory and summed up for each KA.

KA1 Smart Urban Mobility

A large part of the projects deals with KA1, particularly the subcategories KA1.1 and KA1.4. KA1.1 is concerned with access to sustainable mobility options by making transport services more inclusive and attractive, an aim of many projects. Projects with a focus on inclusive mobility involve *CATAPULT*, *Carin_PT*, *VIVALDI*, *SUITS*, *INDIMO*, *SPINE*, *JUST STREETS*, *SMALL*, *UMCASE*, *Fair Mobility* and more. KA1.1 also emphasises the need for sustainable transport solutions in sub- and peri-urban areas. This was recognised by several projects such as *OptiMaaS*, *FastTrack*, *Cities-4-People*, *RECIPROCITY*, *ECCENTRIC* or *INCLUSION*. In addition, promotion of sustainable transport options in urban outskirts is one of the key themes in the 15mC Transition Pathway of the *DUT Call 2022*.

Many projects addressing KA1.1 incorporate elements of KA1.4, which is centred on new technologies in transport. The projects develop, apply, assess, improve, promote technologies and novel concepts and/or use them for their tools and solutions. These technologies include:

- electric and clean vehicles (e.g. *E4-Share*, *DYN@MO*, *GreenCharge*, *GEMINI*, *eHUBS*, *EVOSS*)
- ICT- and GPS-based technologies (e.g. *c3places*, *SUCCESS (FP6)*, *2MOVE2*, *TRACE*, *SYNCHROMODE*, *FORTHCOMING*)
- data collection and management, big data (e.g. *U-PASS*, *MOMENTUM*, *MobiDataLab*, *DISCO*, *SMAPE*, *UMF*, *deployEMDS*)
- traffic management (e.g. *IMTECC*, *2MOVE2*, *DIT4TraM*, *TANGENT*, *SYNCHROMODE*, *Acumen*, *deployEMDS*)
- automated vehicles (e.g. *CATAPULT*, *NICHES+*, *Levitate*, *TANGENT*, *URBANE*, *PAV*, *Dynaxibility4CE*, *LivingLAPT*, *Ride2Autonomy*).

Table 1: Number of related projects to the Key Areas and their subcategories.

Key Area/Subcategory	Number of related projects
KA1 Smart Urban Mobility	173
1. Strengthen access to sustainable mobility options	131
2. Prioritise active mobility and reorganise public space	56
3. Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips	11
4. Integrate new technologies in transport	121
Not specified	22
KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning	135
1. Follow planning principles focussing on sustainability and diversity	80
2. Focus on people-centred public space	37
3. Deploy traffic management for people-centred policies	38
4. Support sustainable lifestyles	51
Not specified	18
KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites	71
1. Support striving neighbourhood economies	17
2. Promote sustainable supply chains and last-mile logistics	38
3. Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery	24
Not specified	21
KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition	186
1. Promote innovative urban governance and create evidence through experiments	149
2. Build on participation and empowerment of civil society	76
3. Foster partnerships that last and engage with stakeholders	69
Not specified	20

KA1.2, which focuses on active mobility, is represented in over a quarter of the projects. The projects *SMART PEDESTRIAN NET* and *WalkUrban* target walking, while *Handshake*, *Bicycle Heroes* and *SPECIFIC* have a focus on cycling. The overarching aim of these projects is to promote active mobility and enhance infrastructure and safety, but some projects chose specific priorities: *PASTA* looks at active mobility through a health perspective and *FLOW* investigates its potential to reduce congestion.

A less commonly addressed topic within the KAs is KA1.3, which aims to find alternatives to cars and flights for travelling between cities, for leisure or for tourism. Longer trips or interurban mobility were seldomly mentioned explicitly. Exceptions are for example *TRANS-FORM* and *SORTEDMobility*, dealing with public transport also in regional and interurban contexts. *MORE*, *HARMONY* and *eCharge4Drivers* were associated with KA1.3 because they consider the Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T).

Although not explicitly stated in KA1, three topics appeared as substantial in relation to sustainable and inclusive mobility:

- Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMPs) (e.g. *TAPforuncertainfuture*, *PROSPERITY*, *SUMPs-Up*, *Park4SUMP*, *REFORM*, *REFOCUS*)
- Public transport (e.g. *Carin-PT*, *CIPTEC*, *SPINE*, *UPPER*, *LivingLAPT*, *UMCASE*, *ERGODIC*)
- Shared mobility (e.g. *EX-TRA*, *DESTINATIONS*, *SUM*, *SMALL*, *COMMON_ACCESS*)

KA2 People-centred Urban Spaces and Planning

KA2 and its subcategories was assigned to 135 projects. KA2.1 asks for people-centred planning principles for land-use and urban development respecting the Functional Urban Area and the environment. This focus is especially prevalent in **DUT**'s 15mC projects. Examples for projects of other funding programmes include:

- *TAPforuncertainfuture* proposes Triple Access Planning, which considers physical mobility, spatial proximity and digital connectivity.
- *EmbedterLabs* is dedicated to improving Urban Living Labs for more synergistic urban planning.
- *ECCENTRIC* looks at integrated and inclusive urban planning approaches.
- *PAV* wants to integrate autonomous vehicles into spatial planning strategies.
- *Dynaxibility4CE* strengthened planning capacities in seven cities and their Functional Urban Areas.

Most projects in KA2.2, which is concerned with redistribution and use of public space, also address KA2.1. Among the 37 projects related to KA2.2, 13 are from **JPI Urban Europe** and the **DUT Partnership** each, showing less interest in the issue by the selected projects found through **CIVITAS** and **POLIS**. *TuneOurBlock*, *StreetForum*, *DESTINATIONS*, *MORE* and *MBD15* deal with the re-allocation and transformation of streets and other spaces. Making public space more inclusive is particularly addressed in *c3places*, *JUST STREETS* and *Inclusive City*. Specific public spaces, namely in large-scale housing estates, are observed by the project *15minESTATES*.

Shifting from land-use back to transport, KA2.3 centres on traffic management with a focus on traffic calming, flexible management solutions and urban access regulations. Traffic safety was an aspect addressed by several projects, such as *LOOPER*, *PASTA* and *PHOEBE*. Many projects, including *GeoSence*, *DIT4TraM*, *TANGENT*, *ACUMEN* and *Ai4LIFE*, develop technological and smart tools for traffic management and *TAAM* wants to offer a toolbox for more agile traffic management strategies or regulations. Projects dedicated to Urban Vehicle Access Regulations are *ReVeAL* and *UVAR Box*.

The fourth subcategory of KA2 "Support sustainable lifestyles" was often addressed with keywords like behavioural change, nudging, incentives and modal shift. *SimpliCITY*, *DyMoN*, *REALLOCATE*, *GreenTurn*, *ShareDiMobiHub* and *SuCoLo* use nudging, while push and pull measures are part of *Park4SUMP* and *UPPER*. Other relevant projects are *MyFairShare*, *EMPOWER* and *MUV*.

KA3 Smart Urban Logistics, Production and Service Sites

Around a third of the examined projects are concerned with KA3 and its subcategories. The major objective is to make supply chains and last-mile logistics more sustainable, the aim of KA3.2. Common approaches in this subcategory include governance and cooperation concepts, cargo-bikes, use of underused infrastructure, consolidation centres, efficient use of urban space, zero-emission or automated vehicles as well as management and planning issues. KA3.2 also mentions Sustainable urban logistics planning (SULP), which is addressed by a few projects, such as *ASAP*, *ULaaDS* and *DISCO*. KA3.2 was also assigned to several projects with a broad scope on sustainable cities and urban transport, like *VIVALDI*, *CARAVEL* or *SPECIFIC*, that recognise the importance of logistics in their efforts.

Innovation is a central issue in the freight-focused projects. However, only 24 projects addressed the specific innovative approaches stated in KA3.3: hybrid solutions for people and goods, shared corporate vehicle fleets, and the use of the 3rd dimension (airspace and underground) for logistics. *ERGODIC* wants to demonstrate modular public transport vehicles for passenger and goods. *2MOVE2* and *metaCCAZE* also work on the integration of personal and freight transport. The project *U-TURN*, *ULaaDS* and *MOVE 21* deal with shared logistics. While the use of airspace is rarely tackled (*ASSURED-UAM*, *NEW NORMAL*), underground applications were not found.

Also rarely addressed by the examined projects was KA3.1 “Support striving neighbourhood economies”. Although many projects considered economic viability or economic efficiency of measures, only 17 projects somehow looked at local manufacturing, use of commercial space or mobile offers of goods and services for undersupplied areas. One showcase project is *SimpliCITY* with local production and consumption as one of their three focuses. *SUNRISE*, *MUV* and *Park4SUMP* had an emphasis on neighbourhoods in connection with local businesses. The project *FRESH* investigates shopping and associated transport in urban and suburban areas in relation to the 15mC concept.

An additional topic in relation to logistics considered in *SINERGI*, *SOUL* and *GreenTurn* are the couriers and their work conditions. The relatively high number of projects not specified in KA3 is due to projects dealing primarily with personal mobility and other topics, but took logistics into account to a minor extend.

KA4 Urban Governance for Mobility Transition

KA4 is the most frequently represented KA, less than 20 projects don’t relate to it. Case studies, living labs and other experiments for creating evidence was found a typical characteristic of the examined projects. But not all experiments were related to policies and thereby don’t fall under KA4.1. Another aspect of KA4.1 are the capacities of authorities. Several projects have responded to this need by designing governance concepts or tools for local authorities, like *GUST*, *DESENT*, *CIVIC* and *SUITS*.

Participative and co-creation approaches involving citizens were frequently used by projects, KA4.2 thus counts 77 projects. Some projects, such as *INDIMO*, *JUST STREETS*, *SMALL* or *InclusiveCity*, focus on vulnerable or excluded groups, including disabled, elderly, ethnic minorities, and socially underprivileged people. Projects with one specific target groups are *City&Co* (elderly), *Metamorphosis*, *CES4Kids* and *Bicycle Heroes* (children), or *Inclusify* and *Fair Mobility* (women). A more general perspective on citizens and users was taken by *ELAN*, *TRACE*, *SUNRISE*, *SENATOR* and *LISTEN*. Projects like *LOOPER*, *Cities-4-People*, *e-smartec* and *DVECE* take a closer look on how to involve citizens in the creation of solutions and the decision-making process. There are also funding programmes dedicated to participation of citizens as **EIT Urban Mobility’s** Citizen Engagement programme and the Science with and for Society (SwafS) **Horizon 2020** programme, which is represented by *WeCount* in the project compilation.

KA4.3 shares similarities with KA4.2, focusing on stakeholder engagement and partnerships. A significant number of projects in this subcategory are logistics-related, for example *CIVIC*, *CityLab*, *Novelog*, *ULaaDS*, *DECARBOMILE* and *UNCHAIN*. One attempt to connect stakeholders is the development of platforms or forums, as in *ASAP*, *SmartHubs*, *U-TURN*, *MobiDataLab*, *RECIPROCITY*, *SMALL* and *FlexCurb*. As in KA4.2, co-creation approaches are often applied to involve stakeholders in projects, which was mentioned by *CIPTEC*, *SPINE*, *InPUT* and *ENACT 15mC*. Frequent terms in the context of KA4.3 are public-private partnerships and collaboration, as used in the descriptions of *TELLUS*, *MEISTER*, *GEMINI*, *MOBI-MIX* and *SMAPE*.

Distribution of projects across the Key Areas

In analysing the examined projects and their relation to the KAs, three subcategories appear to receive limited attention: KA1.3 Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips, KA3.1 Support striving neighbourhood economies and KA3.3 Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery. KA4 was addressed by most projects, as a KA more related to methods (experiments, citizen/stakeholder involvement). The most prevalent KA in terms of topics is KA1.

The distribution of the projects across the KAs is diverse. Notably, 33 projects span across all four KAs, demonstrating a broad engagement with multiple aspects of urban mobility and related themes. Conversely, eight projects targeted a single KA, particularly KA1. The projects *ISA-FIT* and *EVOSS* even exclusively focused on the subcategory KA1.4.

In terms of thematic depth, some projects cover all subcategories within a KA. For instance, *TRANS-FORM* and *SMILE* address all subcategories of KA1, *MOBILIS*, *ELAN* and *Metamorphosis* tackle those of KA2 and *CityLab*, *U-TURN*, *ULaaDS*, *DECARBOMILE* and *FRESH* focus on KA3. For KA4 this applies to 26 projects. The projects with the most comprehensive thematic scope, which engage with the largest number of subcategories, are *MOBILIS*, *SmarterLabs*, *CCCB* and *MoLo Hubs*. In contrast, *ACUTE*, *LENS*, *STREngth_M*, *CIVITAS MUSE* and *SUMI* were only associated with general KAs, aiming to support research and cooperation rather than focusing on specific thematic subcategories (except for *LENS*).

Limitations

This analysis is based on a superficial perspective, relying on limited information about the individual projects. Many project descriptions focus on the objectives, rather than on the actual results and the level of effort invested in the mentioned topics. For example, both projects in KA4.2 and KA4.3 often mention involvement of citizens and/or stakeholders, co-creation or their aim to foster collaboration. However, the degree of participation and the potential to create lasting partnerships, as well as the people-centredness in KA2, are difficult to assess. Other aspects reflected in the projects and their results may not be fully captured, especially for projects with broad thematic scope or when only brief descriptions are available. For instance, active mobility, associated to KA1.2, as a sustainable transport mode is likely featured in other projects without being explicitly mentioned. Furthermore, focal topics, as public transport, and research gaps, as couriers, exist beyond the concept of the KAs.

3.4. Availability of information and resources

A common goal of the projects is to transform the current transport system, making it more accessible, inclusive and sustainable. Given that project lifetimes are limited to only a few years, and case studies often apply to a specific city, neighbourhood or region, it is crucial to ensure that the resources produced during a project are disseminated and remain accessible beyond its conclusion. This supports evidence-based decision-making for authorities and practitioners and enables future projects to build on previous outcomes and experiences, thereby avoiding duplication of effort.

Information and resources of the collected projects were found on the websites of the projects themselves, its funding programmes and partners, and in dedicated repositories. This section first discusses project websites, followed by a brief comparison of the funding programme websites and the repositories. It concludes by assessing the availability of resources in form of documents and tools.

Project websites

Project websites are often taken offline after some time after the project ended. Out of 122 finished projects, for 56 no existing project website could be found. Additionally, nine project websites that were available during the initial data collection had disappeared by September 2024. This concerns both older projects (e.g. *Play!UC*, *Smart Commuting*, *SmarterLabs*, *SMART PEDESTRIAN NET*) and more recent ones that ended in 2023 or even 2024 (e.g. *CATAPULT*, *ITEM*, *LivingLAPT*). Some ongoing projects also lack a dedicated website or are still in the process of establishing one. Nevertheless, some project websites have remained accessible for many years, such as those for *CONCOORD*, *PASTA*, *CIPTEC*, *CityLab*, *CREATE*, *NOVELOG* and *U-TURN*, which ended in 2018 or earlier. Major outcomes of these projects were different kinds of tools and platforms, potentially explaining why their websites were maintained over time.

Funding programme websites and repositories

While project websites often have limited lifespans, funding programme websites can offer a more consistent source of information, usually providing subpages for each of their project. Common features are a project description and a section for facts, such as budget, start and end dates, website link, project coordinator and contact information. There are variations in the information and functions provided both between the funding programmes and within one itself. Table 2 explains how each funding programme presents its projects in dedicated subpages and whether relevant documents are available. “Occasional” highlights those

components whose presence in the project subpages has been noted as particularly variable, but also other items may also be rarely missing or be added.

Table 2: Overview of funding programme websites with a description of information provided on project subpages and availability of documents.

Funding programme & Website	Subpage Structure	Documents
JPI Urban Europe https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/	Abstract, fact box (title, duration, website, contact, budget, partners) <i>Occasional:</i> links to documents, posters	Documents rarely available
CIVITAS Initiative https://civitas.eu/	Project description, links to project website and social media, participating cities, key facts (duration, number of partners, budget, implemented measures), news, resources, contact information, categorisation to thematic areas <i>Occasional:</i> mobility solutions, partners	Documents available in “Resources”
Interreg e.g. https://www.interregnorthsea.eu/ , https://www.interregeurope.eu/	Description, pilot cases, partners, news, events, resources, contact information	Documents available
EIT Urban Mobility https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/	Key facts (programme, duration, coordinator, budget), description, brief dedicated paragraphs (challenges, objectives, output), partners, contact	No documents available
DUT Partnership https://dutpartnership.eu/	No subpages, list of all 15mC projects of the DUT Call 2022: project title, description, coordinator, partners, participating countries <i>Occasional:</i> posters	No documents available

The project descriptions vary in detail and extend. While the *15mC Pathway projects* list of the **DUT Partnership** offers only one or two sentences per project, **JPI Urban Europe** and **CIVITAS** sometimes add descriptions of achieved results and outcomes to subpages older projects. Since the **DUT Partnership** launched its first projects only recently, its approach to present projects, and possibly their results and documents, may evolve over time. With project catalogues of some calls, the “Library” sections of the **JPI Urban Europe**¹ and **DUT Partnership**² websites provide an additional source of information. In contrast to **JPI Urban Europe** and **EIT Urban Mobility**, **CIVITAS** has a large collection of project resources and other documents in their “Resources” section³. For the **Interreg** projects, documents can be found directly in the project subpages. Notably, most examined **Interreg** projects don’t have project websites, but their subpages are highly detailed and structured, making them equivalent to individual project websites.

Like Table 2, Table 3 provides an overview of relevant repositories and which projects and types of information they offer. The following repositories were found as valuable sources of information and documents:

- **ERA-LEARN** is a coordination and support action funded by Horizon Europe running in phases since 2009. The platform acts as a database of partnership initiatives and their action and gives guidance to relevant stakeholders in the R&I partnership community (ERA-LEARN, n.d.).

¹ https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/documents_library/ (retrieved 12 November 2024)

² <https://dutpartnership.eu/media-library/> (retrieved 12 November 2024)

³ <https://civitas.eu/resources> (retrieved 12 November 2024)

- The results and details of projects funded under the **FPs** are accessible through the **Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS)**, a public repository maintained by the Publications Office of the European Union (European Commission, n.d.-a).
- The **keep.eu** database comprises the **Interreg** programmes, projects and documents since the year 2000. It was created and is operated by the Interact programme (Interact, n.d.).
- The **Transport Research and Innovation Monitoring and Information System (TRIMIS)** is a tool by the European Commission to support research, innovation and implementation of transport policies and technologies. It has a focus on the Strategic Transport Research and Innovation Agenda (STRIA), which defines seven thematic transport research areas (European Commission, n.d.-b). The database contains programmes and projects on European and national level, including 90 projects of this compilation, particularly those funded under the FPs.

Additionally, many partners contribute to the distribution and preservation of project information and resources online by reporting on their project involvement. Although in varying degrees of detail, they can sometimes complement the information provided by funding programme websites and databases. For example, the *NICHES+* entry in **CORDIS** does not contain any resources⁴, but the websites of **POLIS**⁵ and **Rupprecht Consult**⁶ do. Universities are also valuable sources of information, and many have repositories for their research.

Table 3: Overview of relevant repositories with involved funding programmes, information provided on project subpages and availability of project documents.

Repository & Website	Funding programmes	Subpage Structure	Documents
ERA-LEARN https://www.era-learn.eu/	JPI Urban Europe, DUT partnership	Acronym, reference number, duration, project topic, network, call, project partners	No documents available
CORDIS https://cordis.europa.eu/	EU Framework Programmes (including CIVITAS)	Project Information box (grant agreement, link to website, DOI, status, dates, funding programme, total cost, EU contribution, coordinator) Sections: “Fact Sheet” (description, objective, fields of science, keywords, details on funding programme and call, coordinator, participants), “Reporting”, “Results” <i>Occasional:</i> “Results in Brief”, “News & Multimedia”	Documents available in “Results” section
keep.eu https://keep.eu/	Interreg	programme, comprehensive and structured description, summary of key facts (name, acronym, duration, status, budget, EU funding, co-financing sources), thematic information, documents, partners	Documents potentially available
TRIMIS https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/	European and member state programmes and projects	fact box (funding, duration, status, geo-spatial type, project cost, project website, acronym, details on transport topics), overview, funding programme <i>Occasional:</i> description of results, partners, documents, technologies	Documents potentially available

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/218504/results> (retrieved 12 November 2024)

⁵ <https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/niches/> (retrieved 12 November 2024)

⁶ <https://www.rupprecht-consult.eu/project/niches-1> (retrieved 12 November 2024)

Availability of resources

As outlined in the tables 2 and 3, funding programme websites and repositories follow different approaches for the provision of project information and documents. In combination with missing project websites, this can result in valuable project outcomes no longer being accessible through public online sources.

During the data collection for the project compilation, various resources, like deliverables, publications, available tools, brochures, presentation materials and other documents, were gathered for completed projects. However, for eight projects funded by **JPI Urban Europe** and three projects funded by **EIT Urban Mobility**, no resources were found. For six of these **JPI Urban Europe** projects, only posters were provided. For four additional projects, results were found in form of tools, programmes or platforms, but not in form of documents. This is for example the *ISA-FIT* product or the Clean Bus Europe Platform by *APOLLO-EU*. In contrast, for projects funded under the **FPs**, **CORDIS** and the **CIVITAS** website usually ensure the availability of documents beyond the project end. For **Interreg**, resources and information are generally on the programme websites for most finished projects and sometimes in **keep.eu**. Still, there are projects from every funding programme, where the low number of discovered documents suggests that some information may be missing from what was once available.

Specific problems in relation to the provision of documents are described in the following chapter.

3.5. Problems faced during the collection of data

The loss of project websites and their resources is just one challenge that complicates the process of accessing valuable information. Both structural and project- or website-specific issues can impact the quality of the project compilation and the findings of this analysis. Additionally, this section contains some advice for conducting such kind of data collections.

Missing and outdated information

Without project websites available, often there is only a short paragraph, describing problems and objectives. As a result, much of the knowledge and solutions developed cannot be used for further research or application. It also complicates determining keywords and categorising to the KAs. However, as discussed above, some funding programme and repositories succeed to maintain a significant amount information and resources.

Another major issue is the infrequent updating of websites, especially regarding links to project websites and documents on funding programme websites. They often refer to project websites that no longer exist. Some subpages of **JPI Urban Europe** contain links to documents that were removed when the project website was taken offline (e.g. *E4-Share*⁷, *LOOPER*⁸). A positive exception is found in the *GUST* project subpage⁹, where the handbook as main result was still accessible, located on a publications repository by the coordinating university¹⁰.

On the other hand, funding programme websites often lack links to websites for newer projects. For instance, the **DUT Partnership** website doesn't mention any project websites for their *15mC Pathway projects*¹¹, though ten websites could be discovered through searches. Similarly, three websites of *Sino-European ENUAC* projects were detected, despite not being linked on their **JPI Urban Europe** subpages.

A positive example is the case of the *c3places* project: its initial project website was replaced by a website created by a partner university¹². The project's **JPI Urban Europe** subpage updated the link to the new

⁷ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/e4-share/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁸ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/looper/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁹ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/gust/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹⁰ https://lup.lub.lu.se/search/ws/files/27224276/Urban_Living_Labs_Handbook.pdf (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹¹ https://dutpartnership.eu/funding-opportunities/dut_call_2022/funded-projects/15mc-projects/ (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹² <https://myc3place.di.unimi.it> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

website¹³. Unfortunately, the new website itself still contains links to the initial website, whose URL is not related to the project anymore.

Repositories were also partly incomplete. The *ERA-NET Cofund Urban Transformation Capacities (ENUTC) calls* are not listed on the **ERA-LEARN** subpage for **JPI Urban Europe**¹⁴, although the ERA-NET including its calls and projects exists in the repository¹⁵. The funded projects of the *Sino-European ENUAC call*¹⁶ and the *DUT Call 2022*¹⁷ are not featured in the **ERA-LEARN**. On **keep.eu** the most recent **Interreg** project of the compilation, *REFOCUS*, could not be found. Some of these missing entries may still be added over time.

Project partner websites can serve as additional sources of information. For the project compilation, universities were of particular interest for the purpose of identifying the participating departments. Despite the use of several search methods, this was not always achieved. In some cases, projects could not be found at all on university websites, a situation common for newly launched or long-completed projects. For instance, the search for *ACUTE*, with duration 2022 to 2024, yielded no results on the **Malmö University** website¹⁸.

Differing and variable information

Variations in partner names posed additional challenges for precise allocation. Organisations might change names, merge with or be acquired with another organisation. Additionally, it was important to keep language differences in mind, as partners sometimes were listed in English and other times in their native language. This was mitigated by including both labels, as well as abbreviations, in the partner spreadsheet where necessary.

Different sources might not only use diverse labels for the same partner, but their partner list may also vary slightly. Such discrepancies arise partly from definitions, as participation in projects sometimes extends beyond the official partners and can take different forms. The *DUT Call 2022* Project catalogue distinguishes between “Project partners” and “Cooperation partners” (DUT Partnership, 2024a). In *MIMIC*, there are 14 “Letter of interest-partners” presented on the website¹⁹. The *JUSTICE* website lists more project partners²⁰ than indicated in its **JPI Urban Europe**²¹ and **ERA-LEARN**²² entries. In most cases, only the partners indicated on the funding programme websites and repositories were considered for the spreadsheet. An exception was the project *FlexCurb*, whose partner list on the **EIT Urban Mobility** subpage²³, in comparison to the information by **POLIS**²⁴, lacked **FIT Consulting** and **POLIS** itself.

A speciality of **EIT Urban Mobility** subpages lies in the indication of project partners solely through logos, which complicated their identification. For example, the partner in the project *LivingLAPT*²⁵ whose logo

¹³ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/c3places/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹⁴ <https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/urban-europe> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹⁵ <https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/enutc> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹⁶ <https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹⁷ <https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/driving-urban-transitions/dut-call-2022> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹⁸ <https://mau.se/en/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

¹⁹ <https://closer.lindholmen.se/projekt/mimic-aiming-sustainable-construction-logistics> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²⁰ <https://justice-project.eu/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²¹ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/justice/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²² <https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/en-uac/1st-en-auc-joint-cofund-call/joining-urban-morphology-spatio-temporal-and-socio-cognitive-accessibility-for-an-inclusive-city-environment> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²³ <https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/flexcurb/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²⁴ <https://www.polisnetwork.eu/project/flexcurb/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²⁵ <https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/projects/livinglapt-2/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

consists of the letter “R” on a green background, could with some effort be identified as the **Municipality of Říčany**²⁶.

Moreover, project partners can change during the project lifetime, and not all sources are up to date. One example is the project *SMILE*, where one of its participants listed in **CORDIS** was “**CTP**” from Italy, without information on address or website provided²⁷. This organisation was not identified in the partner spreadsheet at this point, and an internet search was not successful to find a more precise name. The project’s final report clarified the situation: **CTP** was a public transport provider in one of the *SMILE* cities, which was replaced by another company by the city. This resulted in a change of project partners and notably had an impact on the project’s progress (Lewis et al., 2009).

Even project names and acronyms were not always clear or consistently used. On **JPI Urban Europe**’s subpage for the *BREATHE*, “*Urban form, location choice and transport solutions for low-carbon cities*”²⁸ is given as full title, whereas the project coordinator adds “*Building Resilient Economic Agglomerations addressing Transportation and Health Effects*”²⁹ in front, explaining the origin of the short title “*BREATHE*”. When searching for a specific project on the internet or a website, it was perceived as useful to try both short and long titles, consider alternative spellings, and use native language settings of websites if necessary. For instance, neither a search for “*ENUAC*” nor “*EN-UAC*” on **CORDIS**, but only the long title “*ERA-NET Urban Accessibility and Connectivity*” delivered the correct result. The project *e-MATS* was found on the **Politehnica University Timișoara**’s research-dedicated website, available only in Romanian language. By navigating through the website, looking for sections dedicated to projects, the university division responsible for *e-MATS* was identified³⁰.

When working with **CORDIS**, users should be aware that older **FPs** and their projects have been archived and must be explicitly selected to be included in search queries. A grant agreement number can facilitate the process of finding a project in the repository. Otherwise, various filters can help narrow down the search results.

Start and end dates can differentiate between the sources as well. For example, while the *ERA-NET Cofund Smart Urban Futures (ENSUF) call* opened in December 2015 according to **JPI Urban Europe**³¹, the *ERA-NET Cofund* has a start date in May 2016 in **CORDIS**³². Finding dates for the *DUT Partnership*’s projects was difficult, as they were neither mentioned on the website nor the project catalogue. For several other projects, especially from some *JPI Urban Europe* calls, only annual figures and no exact dates were found.

A fortunately rarely encountered problem concerns mistakes on the various websites. One was observed in **CORDIS** for the project *TELLUS*, where key objectives of “*ROTORS*” are described³³. All other information aligned with those provided by **CIVITAS**³⁴. A more general issue was determined on the **EIT Urban Mobility** website. It allows users to filter the funded projects by programme and year, but most programmes return no results³⁵.

²⁶ <https://www.ricany.cz/en/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513518> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²⁸ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/breathe/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

²⁹ <https://vu.nl/en/about-vu/faculties/school-of-business-and-economics/more-about/breathe> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³⁰ <http://www.research.upt.ro/page11.html#header02-8w4> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³¹ <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/ensuf-call/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/693443> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/11991> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³⁴ <https://civitas.eu/projects/tellus> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³⁵ <https://www.eiturbanmobility.eu/our-activities/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

Resources

As previously mentioned, project resources can disappear with project websites, but repositories and partner websites can maintain documents publicly available. However, during the data collection, a mismatch was observed between documents on the project websites and those in the relating repositories, and sometimes project partner websites. Documents available on the project website can miss in the repositories, and the same vice-versa. To ensure one gathered all available documents, it is necessary to check the different sources and compare the documents. This can be difficult due to different or missing structures and labelling. For the project *CCCB*, **CORDIS** provides 12 deliverables and a few publications³⁶, while the project website offers plenty resources of different types³⁷, but still not all deliverables available in **CORDIS**. **CIVITAS** “Resources” for *CCCB* contains a few of the produced guides, along with some joint resources from multiple **CIVITAS** projects³⁸.

Special attention is required with the **CIVITAS** “Resources” section, where the one document can appear multiple times. For example, filtering the documents for the project *MIMOSA* yields 128 entries³⁹, including four entries for the deliverable “Measure Result - Long Term Evaluation Flexible Access for Cleaner Freight Traffic in Utrecht”⁴⁰, as well as two entries with different labels and types of resources, but both leading to the same brochure “Innovative cities - Before and after CIVITAS”⁴¹.

4. Conclusion, recommendations and future directions

The project compilation represents a snapshot of R&I projects centred around accessible and sustainable urban transport. Originating from the *ENUAC projects*, it primarily consists of projects from **JPI Urban Europe** and its successor, the **DUT Partnership**, as well as **CIVITAS**. To reflect the broader landscape of transport-related research, it also contains projects of the **EU Framework Programmes**, **Interreg**, **EIT Urban Mobility** and a few other projects, including some projects with a focus on technology rather than accessibility and inclusion.

This final chapter summarises the main findings of the analysis, offers recommendations for funding programmes and ongoing projects, and outlines potential applications of the project compilation.

4.1. Conclusions

A notable finding from the analysis of project consortia is the contrast in participation among organisations. While the majority of project partners are involved in only one project, a small group of organisations participates in more than ten projects each. Between the projects, large variations in consortia size and connections to other projects through shared partners were observed. Projects with large consortia are more likely to share partners with many other projects and to have multiple partners in common. A high number of shared partners between two projects can also indicate the continuation of a successful collaboration through a new project. Among the 203 projects, four are isolated in terms of shared partners. On average, **JPI Urban Europe** and **DUT Partnership** projects possess less and weaker connections compared to those of the **FPS**, **Interreg** and **EIT Urban Mobility**. An important finding is the significant impact of the most frequently involved partners on these connections.

³⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/769086/results> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³⁷ <https://cyclelogistics.eu/resources/deliverables/>, <https://cyclelogistics.eu/resources/guides-publications/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³⁸ <https://civitas.eu/resources?f%5B0%5D=project%3A47147> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

³⁹ https://civitas.eu/resources?f%5B0%5D=project%3A2933&search_api_fulltext= (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁴⁰ <https://civitas.eu/resources/measure-result-long-term-evaluation-flexible-access-for-cleaner-freight-traffic-in-2> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁴¹ <https://civitas.eu/resources/innovative-cities-before-and-after-civitas> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

All projects share the common aim to contribute to more accessible, inclusive and sustainable urban areas. Some projects focus on concepts or technologies, while others address specific neighbourhood or city types. Passenger mobility received attention from more projects than logistics, although many projects dealt with transport in general. Several research gaps have been identified based on the concept of the KAs:

- KA1.3 Provide sustainable solutions for longer trips
- KA3.1 Support striving neighbourhood economies
- KA3.3 Test and diffuse innovative approaches to logistics and delivery; particularly in regard of the use of airspace and underground for logistics

KA4 “Urban governance for mobility transition” was recognised as a methodological KA, with KA4.1 particularly applying to many projects.

The analysis of the projects revealed the interconnections of urban transport issues with other research areas, and thereby the need for comprehensive urban transformations. This is evident in the concept of the KAs, which emphasises land-use, sustainable lifestyles and manufacturing, as well as in several projects integrating health (e.g. *PASTA*, *MUV*, *JiM*), energy (e.g. *BREATHE*, *me²*, *GreenCharge*), and participation (e.g. *playIUC*, *SmartGov*, *DVECE*). By expressing the need for sustainable transport options in sub- and peri-urban areas and for longer trips, the KAs also draw attention on the importance of research beyond urban centres and city borders.

However, the longevity of project resources is a concern, as project websites often have limited lifespans. Funding programme websites and repositories are either not intended to provide project resources or, in some cases, fail to offer all the resources that were once publicly available.

A joint and comprehensive platform or repository to consolidate the research efforts in this area is absent, although the collected projects share a common link through their connection to the **EU Framework Programmes** and the European Commission. Many of them are directly funded under the **FPs**. **JPI Urban Europe**, the **DUT Partnership** and **EIT Urban Mobility** are enabled and partly co-funded by the EU, and **Interreg** is part of the EU’s Cohesion Policy. However, with **TRIMIS** a platform dedicated to transport research and innovation in the EU exists. It also encompasses efforts undertaken at the national level and outside the urban context. Despite its primary technological agenda, the repository features various of the examined projects related to accessibility and inclusion, such as *LOOPER*⁴², *Metamorphosis*⁴³ or *INCLUSION*⁴⁴. Unfortunately, only 90 of the 203 projects were found in this repository, and the data provided is varying.

4.2. Recommendations

Based on these relevant findings, this section presents recommendations aimed at improving the sustainability, dissemination, and impact of R&I projects in sustainable urban transport. Some suggestions are long-term goals, while others focus on more immediate, practical steps.

One long-term recommendation is the creation of a joint repository, to archive project information and resources. This repository would ideally either centralise a broad range of research activities supported by the EU or focus specifically on research areas as transport or urban transformations, which could also include

⁴² <https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/learning-loops-public-realm> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁴³ <https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/transformation-neighbourhoods-child-friendly-way-increase-quality-life-all-citizens> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁴⁴ <https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/towards-more-accessible-and-inclusive-mobility-solutions-european-prioritised-areas> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

national and regional efforts. Given the challenges that might be related to the development and management of such a platform, several more feasible approaches could be considered:

One possibility is to expand **CORDIS** to include projects from partnerships tied to the **FPs**, such as the ERA-NET Cofunds and the **DUT Partnership**.

For a transport-related repository, **TRIMIS** could be enhanced by funding programmes demanding projects to contribute to the repository. Additionally, its technology-focused agenda should be updated to reflect a more comprehensive view on transport issues.

A joint repository alone can't solve the problem of unavailable information. Communication and the transfer of information and resources from projects to current and future repositories as well as their funding programme, and subsequently to interested stakeholders, remain important. Improved coordination is needed to effectively pass on and update information to improve dissemination of project outputs and their sustainability.

For projects, particularly those whose funding programmes don't currently offer a repository for project resources, it is recommended to take precautions. They need to think early enough about the future location and dissemination of their resources, both documents and tools, and how they will manage them once the project ended. This might involve ensuring the maintenance of the project website for several years or submitting the project, preferably including documents, to **TRIMIS** and other dedicated platforms. During the project compilation, several platforms focusing on specific topics were discovered, such as the Clean Bus Europe Platform⁴⁵ by *APOLLO-EU* or the EU Urban Mobility Observatory specialised on SUMP⁴⁶. Tools might be outsourced to project partner websites and shared in the **CIVITAS** Urban Mobility Tool Inventory⁴⁷.

Funding programmes can support their projects by providing extended funding specifically dedicated to securing and disseminating project outcomes. This would, for example, allow longer maintenance of the website or the continued management of developed tools. Durable websites and resources are currently achieved by **Interreg's** approach, where project subpages are equivalent replacements for separated project websites. Further insights are needed to evaluate whether this approach could be of interest for other funding programme.

Based on the analysis of the KAs, future funding calls and projects should address the identified research gaps. These include developing sustainable solutions for longer trips (KA1.3), supporting production and commercial activities at neighbourhood-scale (KA3.1), and integrating the 3rd dimension in city logistics (KA3.3).

4.3. Future directions

The project compilation and the insights from this analysis can support future funding decisions and consortium formation as well as engage actors to improve availability of information and resources:

- The analysis of KAs as well as project consortia can provide insights for future funding allocation.
- The collection of participating organisations can aid in forming new consortia by identifying experienced partners in related projects.
- The recommendations outlined above, as well as the various problems encountered during the data collection, can be taken into account by funding programmes, repositories and projects.

⁴⁵ <https://cleanbusplatform.eu/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁴⁶ <https://urban-mobility-observatory.transport.ec.europa.eu/> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

⁴⁷ <https://civitas.eu/tool-inventory> (retrieved 6 November 2024)

To secure the resources available, documents and links to other resources from completed projects have been preserved during the data collection. This is one aspect that the project compilation provides as basis for more detailed research, for example:

- The project compilation offers a starting point for in-depth evaluations of specific topics or funding programmes.
- The analyses of project consortia could continue by evaluating participation of different partner types (e.g. universities, cities, companies) and their geographic origins, with a potential focus on coordinators and work package leaders. Interviews and surveys might give insights on informal roles.
- Case studies could be investigated regarding their distribution among cities and their long-term local impact.
- Through an in-depth analysis of projects and their outcomes, the contributions to the KAs and their subcategories could be graded and specific activities collected.
- A more differentiated categorisation of project topics, for instance using the **CIVITAS** thematic areas or an elaborated set of keywords, could supplement the KAs.
- Applying a word analysis tool, as developed by WP4 of the *ACUTE* project, could provide an additional perspective on the project compilation.

References

- DUT Partnership. (2024a). *Projects Catalogue DUT Call 2022*. <https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Project-Catalogue-Edited-09.2024-one-page.pdf>
- DUT Partnership. (2024b, March). *Position Paper – Navigating the 15-minute City: First Learnings and Discussions from the Driving Urban Transitions Partnership* (L. Zeisel, M. Jäger, & K. Hanna, Eds.). DUT Partnership. https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/DUT_15mC-Position-Paper_digital_final.pdf
- ERA-LEARN. (n.d.). *About—ERA-LEARN*. ERA-LEARN. Retrieved 31 July 2024, from <https://www.era-learn.eu/service/about>
- European Commission. (n.d.-a). *About CORDIS*. CORDIS | European Commission. Retrieved 3 September 2024, from <https://cordis.europa.eu/about>
- European Commission. (n.d.-b). *About TRIMIS*. TRIMIS. Retrieved 17 September 2024, from <http://trimis.ec.europa.eu/about-trimis>
- European Commission. (2014, September 22). *SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Smart, Green And Integrated Transport*. CORDIS | European Commission. <https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020-EU.3.4>
- Interact. (n.d.). *About keep.eu*. Keep.Eu. Retrieved 17 September 2024, from <https://keep.eu/about-keep-eu/>
- JPI Urban Europe. (n.d.-a). *About the calls*. JPI Urban Europe. Retrieved 19 July 2024, from <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/calls/intro/>
- JPI Urban Europe. (n.d.-b). *ACUTE - Accessibility and Connectivity knowledge hub for Urban Transformation in Europe*. JPI Urban Europe. Retrieved 1 August 2024, from <https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/acute-accessibility-and-connectivity-knowledge-hub-for-urban-transformation-in-europe/>
- JPI Urban Europe. (2021). *ENUAC Projects Catalogue 2021*. https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/ENUAC-projects-catalogue_upd-081021_webb.pdf
- Lewis, A., Stivan, J., & Jones, S. (2009). *SMILE Final Evaluation Report*. <https://civitas.eu/sites/default/files/civitas20smile20final20evaluation20report.pdf>